

Review articles

Resources and Opportunities Available for Allopathic and Osteopathic Medical Students Pursuing Otolaryngology: A Comprehensive Analysis

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Background

Otolaryngology is a surgical subspecialty dedicated to addressing conditions of the head and neck. It is no surprise that matching into surgical subspecialties such as otolaryngology-head and neck surgery becomes increasingly competitive each year. Data indicate that each year on average, students are performing at higher levels than years previous. This increase in competitiveness prompts the development of resources including specialty-specific information to be made more readily available to students. This review aims to identify key otolaryngology organizations in the United States that may offer valuable resources for medical students such as research, conference scholarships, mentorship programs, and avenues for leadership roles. The central objective is to underscore resources capable of providing medical students with the skills and experiences vital for pursuing an otolaryngology residency.

Methods

177 organizations were identified by the University of North Texas Health Science Center (UNTHSC) Gibson Library and four independent researchers. After eliminating duplicates and screening for relevance, eleven national otolaryngology-head and neck surgery organizations were selected for evaluation, focusing on key criteria such as membership eligibility and resources available for medical students.

Results

The comprehensive analysis highlighted resources and opportunities available for allopathic and osteopathic medical students pursuing otolaryngology as a career. These entities offer numerous benefits, including research opportunities, educational materials, annual meetings, and access to subspecialty learning. These organizations can provide a foundation of resources to medical students who take advantage of their associated benefits.

Conclusion

This analysis underscores the vital support that professional organizations offer to medical students pursuing otolaryngology, highlighting the significance of mentorship, research opportunities, and educational materials. It urges medical students to actively engage with these organizations to enhance their career prospects. However, identified gaps in mentorship, travel financial aid, and leadership roles point towards areas needing enhancement.

INTRODUCTION

Otolaryngology is a surgical subspecialty dedicated to addressing conditions of the head and neck. It is no surprise that matching into surgical subspecialties such as otolaryngology-head and neck surgery increases in competitiveness each year.¹ The data indicate that, on average, students perform at higher levels each year compared to previous years.^{2,3} This increase in competitiveness prompts the de-

velopment of resources including specialty-specific information to be made more readily available to students, which can in turn allow students to become more “successful residents”.⁴ One of the critical determinants for those considering a career in otolaryngology is the availability of resources for medical students as they prepare their residency applications. Additionally, there exists a prevalent lack of comprehensive exposure to the field, partly due to limited course material within the standard medical cur-

Figure 1. PRISMA chart detailing the study design.

riculum. In addition, these gaps in resources and exposure are notable among medical students who may lack direct access to affiliated otolaryngology programs (“home programs”).^{5,6}

Despite these proposed barriers, resources are available to assist students in navigating a career in otolaryngology.⁷ This review seeks to highlight and compile essential otolaryngology organizations and their resources in the United States.

Through an analysis of these organizations, this study reveals opportunities available to medical students through organizations such as research opportunities, conference scholarships, mentorship programs, and avenues for leadership roles. The central objective is to underscore resources capable of providing medical students with the necessary skills and experiences vital for pursuing an otolaryngology residency.^{8,9}

Included in the analysis is a total of eleven national organizations highlighted by the researchers that met specific selection criteria.

METHODOLOGY

The data used in this analysis was collected in October of 2023.

SELECTION CRITERIA

In the initial phase of this research, a comprehensive investigation was conducted to identify organizations relevant to otolaryngology. 147 organizations were identified by the University of North Texas Health Science Center (UNTHSC) Gibson Library while an additional 30 organizations were identified by four independent researchers in a thorough

online search. The combination of these sources resulted in a preliminary list of 177 organizations. Three duplicates were eliminated, thus decreasing the list to 174 unique organizations.

The next stage of screening was predicated on the relevance of these organizations to the field of otolaryngology. Three independent researchers reviewed all sources and excluded 129 entities due to not being specific to the field of otolaryngology-head and neck surgery.

A set of precise criteria was then established; specifically, the organizations were required to (1) permit enrollment of physicians, (2) conduct annual meetings, (3) operate on a national level, and (4) permit involvement of medical students. This selection process yielded thirteen organizations that met the specified criteria. However, upon further scrutiny, two additional organizations were identified and subsequently removed, finalizing a cohort of eleven national otolaryngology-head and neck surgery organizations for comprehensive evaluation.

DATA COLLECTION

The websites of all eleven national organizations were reviewed independently by the researchers. Information related to subspecialty, osteopathic and allopathic student admission, research opportunities for medical students, mentorships for medical students, cost to join the national organization, cost to attend the annual meeting, leadership opportunities, scholarships available, and educational materials offered were gathered, and organized (Table 1). Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data collected.

RESULTS

RESOURCES AVAILABLE FOR ALLOPATHIC AND OSTEOPATHIC STUDENTS THROUGH PROFESSIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

ORGANIZATION FOCUSES ON DISCIPLINES OR SUBSPECIALTIES WITHIN OTOLARYNGOLOGY

Approximately 46% (n=5) of the organizations included in the review (n=11) are dedicated to subspecialties or specific focuses within the field of otolaryngology. These organizational focuses included Rhinology,¹⁰ Pediatrics,¹¹ Laryngology,¹² Dysphagia,¹³ and Craniofacial Reconstruction.¹⁴

ORGANIZATION ALLOWS BOTH MD AND DO STUDENT MEMBERSHIP

A concern that medical students express is uncertainty whether organizations allow osteopathic student involvement. 100% of organizations included in the review (n=11) allowed open enrollment to both allopathic and osteopathic medical students.

MEDICAL STUDENT COST TO JOIN ORGANIZATION

Membership fees influence medical students' decisions regarding joining organizations, attending conferences, and accessing learning materials. 55% (n=6) of the organizations in this review (n=11) have listed registration fees for joining their organization on their websites ([Table 1](#)).¹⁵⁻²⁰ The average cost of registering as a member for organizations that charge medical students a registration fee was \$57. Five (45%) of the organizations included in the review do not charge medical students to register as a member if specific criteria are met.

ANNUAL MEETING, RESEARCH PRESENTED AT ANNUAL MEETING, AND MEDICAL STUDENTS CAN PRESENT AT ANNUAL MEETING

100% (n=11) of the reviewed organizations have annual meetings that medical students can attend. Of the organizations conducting annual meetings included in this review, ten allow medical students to present research ([Table 1](#)).

MEDICAL STUDENT REGISTRATION FEE FOR ANNUAL MEETINGS

Approximately 82% (n=9) of the reviewed organizations (n=11) charge a registration fee for their annual conference ([Table 1](#)).¹⁰⁻²⁰ Including the 18% (n=2) of conferences that provide free meeting registration for students, the average cost for a medical student to register for an annual meeting is between \$109.64 and \$152.73. This range is attributed to certain conferences offering students the option to register for specific conference days, rather than the entire multi-day event.

ANNUAL MEETING REGISTRATION / TRAVEL SCHOLARSHIPS AVAILABLE FOR MEDICAL STUDENTS

Conference travel expenses can significantly impact students depending on their proximity to the conference venue and whether their medical school provides financial support for conference travel. Among the organizations reviewed (n=11), only two offer a registration or travel scholarship to medical students ([Table 2](#)).^{21,22} These scholarships are typically awarded on an application-based process, requiring the completion of a detailed application, and meeting specific criteria, such as submitting a first-author abstract.²²

MENTORSHIP AVAILABLE WITHIN THE ORGANIZATION FOR MEDICAL STUDENTS

For numerous medical students, networking with established residents and physicians in their fields can pose a daunting and significant challenge. Two of the eleven organizations reviewed (18%) have dedicated mentorship programs available to medical students.^{23,24} These initiatives serve as invaluable platforms for students to connect with mentors who can offer guidance and support through a demanding application process ([Table 3](#)).

LEADERSHIP OPPORTUNITIES AVAILABLE FOR MEDICAL STUDENTS

Another opportunity that students seek out during medical school is leadership. Only one of the included organizations offered leadership opportunities to medical students. The National Otolaryngology Interest Group (NOIG) offers leadership opportunities at a to medical students. NOIG leadership, in collaboration with the greater Headmirror team, is tasked with increasing awareness and promoting student education in otolaryngology, recruiting resident and faculty mentors, and delivering to its student members resources to aid in preparation for a successful match into otolaryngology residency.

SCHOLARSHIPS/GRANTS AVAILABLE FOR MEDICAL STUDENTS

Many organizations have taken steps to mitigate the financial strain that medical students may face. 55% (n=6) of the eleven reviewed organizations offer scholarships, grants, or awards to medical students outside of travel scholarships ([Table 4](#)).²⁵⁻²⁸

EDUCATIONAL MATERIAL AVAILABLE TO MEDICAL STUDENTS

As medical students prepare for rotations and USMLE/COMLEX boards, many seek additional learning materials from outside sources. 91% (n=10) of the eleven organizations included in the study provide accessible educational material to registered members of their organizations. This educational material encompasses a wide array of materials, ranging from original content produced by the organi-

Organization	Organization Focuses on a Subspecialty of Otolaryngology	Organization Allows Both MD and DO Student Membership	Medical Student Cost to Join Organization	Annual Meeting	Research Presented at Annual Meeting	Medical Students can Present at Annual Meeting	Medical Student Registration Fee for Annual Meeting	Annual Meeting Registration / Travel Scholarships Available	Mentorship Available Within the Organization	Leadership Opportunities Available	Scholarships / Grants Available	Educational Material Available
American Academy of Otolaryngology–Head and Neck Surgery	No	Yes	\$30	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$195	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
The American Osteopathic Colleges of Ophthalmology and Otolaryngology – Head and Neck Surgery (AOCCO-HNS)	No	Yes	\$0	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$100	No	No	No	No	Yes
American Head and Neck Society	No	Yes	\$25	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$300	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
American Rhinologic Society (ARS)	Yes	Yes	\$0	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$0	No	No	No	No	No
Society for Ear, Nose, and Throat Advancement in Children (SENTAC)	Yes	Yes	\$100	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$250	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
American College of Surgeons (ACS) - Otolaryngology / Head and Neck Surgery	No	Yes	\$0	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$15	No	No	No	No	Yes
National Otolaryngology Interest Group	No	Yes	\$0	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$0	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Association for Research in Otolaryngology (ARO)	No	Yes	\$50	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$200	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
Dysphagia Research Society	Yes	Yes	\$50	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$95-195*	No	No	No	No	Yes
American Cleft Palate-Craniofacial Association	Yes	Yes	\$30	Yes	Yes	Yes	\$50	No	No	No	No	Yes
The Voice Foundation	Yes	Yes	\$0	Yes	No	No	\$10-375*	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Total Organizational Involvement Averages and Associated Average Costs	5	11	\$57	11	10	10	\$109.64-152.73*	2	2	1	6	10

Table 1. Shown are the eleven organizations included in the review. Variables relevant to medical students included in the review comprised: Organization Focuses on a Subspecialty of Otolaryngology, Organization Allows Both MD and DO Student Membership, Medical Student Cost to Join Organization, Annual Meeting, Research Presented at Annual Meeting, Medical Students can Present at Annual Meeting, Medical Student Registration Fee for Annual Meeting, Annual Meeting Registration/Travel Scholarships Available for Medical Students, Mentorship Available Within the Organization for Medical Students, Leadership Opportunities Available for Medical Students, Scholarships/Grants Available for Medical Students, Educational Material Available to Medical Students. Fees associated with “Medical Student Cost to Join Organization” are annual. Average costs for this category were calculated if the organization charged registration fees. Annual Meeting registration fees indicated with an asterisk (*) denotes that the registration fee is variable and dependent upon limiting factors. All registration fees shown assume the medical student has successfully enrolled in/purchased an organizational membership and qualified for respective “early- bird” deadlines.

Organization	Registration/Travel Scholarships Available for Medical Students	Award Available
American Academy of Otolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery (AAOHNS)	Yes	Medical Student Travel Grants
Association for Research in Otolaryngology (ARO)	Yes	ARO Travel Award
Triological Society**	Yes	Travel Awards
Combined Otolaryngology Spring Meetings (COSM)**	Yes	Medical Student Travel Awards

Note: Travel awards offered vary between organizations, with differing amounts allocated based on the applicant's geographical location and placement within the reward system (e.g. ARO awards \$500 for U.S. candidates, \$750 for international candidates, and \$1,500 for the highest-scored applicant in a reward category).²²

**While not meeting the selection criteria for this study, both the Triological Society and COSM offer medical students generous travel scholarships.^{23,24}

Table 2. Travel Awards Available for Medical Students. Includes the organizations and the associated awards available.

Organization	Mentorship Available for Medical Students	Mentorship Program
American Academy of Otolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery	Yes	AAOHNS mENTor
National Otolaryngology Interest Group	Yes	National Otolaryngology Interest Group (NOIG) Mentee Sign-Up

Note: Requirements for involvement in the respective programs vary depending on the affiliated organization; all necessitate an application and matching process.

Table 3. Mentorship Available Within the Organization for Medical Students. Includes the names of the mentee/mentorship programs.

zations themselves to referenced materials made accessible to registered students (Table 5).

DISCUSSION

In this comprehensive analysis of resources and opportunities available for allopathic and osteopathic medical students pursuing otolaryngology, we have highlighted the pivotal role of national organizations in providing a structured support system.⁶ These entities offer numerous benefits, including research opportunities, educational materials, annual meetings, and access to subspecialties. These

organizations can provide a competitive edge to medical students who take advantage of these benefits.

Furthermore, all eleven organizations allow membership from both MD and DO students, reflecting a commitment to diversity and accessibility in the field of otolaryngology.

In addition to the organizations reviewed, other otolaryngology entities offer medical students valuable resources such as travel grants, networking, and research opportunities. Many organizations that did not meet the selection criteria for this review have conferences hosted at the annual Combined Otolaryngology Spring Meetings (COSM). COSM brings together organizations related to otolaryngology including the American Academy of Facial

Organization	Medical Student Grants / Awards	Grant & Award Details
American Academy of Otolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery	Yes	Conference Travel Grant, Diversity Endowment URM Away Rotation Grant, Humanitarian Travel Grants
American Head and Neck Society	Yes	AHNS Pilot Grant, Presidential Awards, Research Grant, Research Award
Association for Research in Otolaryngology (ARO)	Yes	Awards available for best in research
The Voice Foundation	Yes	Annual Symposium Research Awards, Annual Symposium Educational Opportunity Award, Gala Awards
National Otolaryngology Interest Group	Yes	Rotation Travel Grants. Partner with various organizations to advertise awards and scholarships.
Society for Ear, Nose, and Throat Advancement in Children (SENTAC)	Yes	The Dana M. Thompson Diversity, Equity & Inclusion Award, Gray Humanitarian Award, Ruben Scientific Achievement Award

Note: Eligibility for these financial aids may entail formal application processes or meeting specific prerequisites tailored to each grant. Research rewards are awarded at the discretion of conference judges and panelists.

Table 4. Scholarships/Grants Available for Medical Students.

Plastic and Reconstructive Surgery (AAFPRS), American Broncho-Esophagological Association (ABEA), American Head and Neck Society (AHNS), American Laryngological Association (ALA), American Neurotology Society (ANS), American Otological Society (AOS), American Rhinologic Society (ARS), American Society of Pediatric Otolaryngology (ASPO), and The Triological Society (TRIO).²⁹ These meetings serve as platforms for networking, research, and education for medical students. Of notable mention is the Triological Society, which did not meet the inclusion criteria for this review but boasts generous travel scholarships available to medical students (Table 2).³⁰

The availability of resources and opportunities for medical students interested in pursuing a career in otolaryngology extends beyond traditional professional organizations.³¹ Notably, platforms such as Otomatch and The Auricle, despite not meeting the selection criteria, provide invaluable peer and physician-led assistance. These platforms facilitate a collaborative environment where medical students can access and share a wealth of information and guidance. Resources available through these organizations include flashcard decks tailored for otolaryngology rotations, podcast links offering insights into various aspects of

the specialty, virtual chat channels that serve as forums for real-time question-and-answer opportunities among peers and mentors, and opportunities to showcase research in weekly newsletter issues.^{32,33}

In addition, Doximity is an important tool for medical students navigating the complex landscape of residency applications. By offering a comprehensive platform that allows applicants to filter and select residency programs based on specific criteria, Doximity streamlines the process of identifying potential residency programs that students may be interested in applying to. Furthermore, the platform offers medical students details regarding possible away and audition rotations, allowing them to explore and plan accordingly with specifics in mind. Access to these platforms is free for medical students, and utilization of such resources is highly encouraged.³⁴

It is evident that while the current system provides a solid foundation of support for medical students interested in otolaryngology, there is a clear opportunity for growth.³¹ Expanding financial support, mentorship/leadership opportunities, and leveraging peer-led platforms can enhance the training and development of future otolaryngologists.⁶ As the field continues to evolve, so too should the resources

Organization	Educational Material Available	Educational Material Available / Referenced
American Academy of Otolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery	Yes	OTO Logic Learning Network - education portal with expert series, webcasts, patient scenarios, clinical practice guidelines, eCourses, ENT Exam Video Series, and eBooks. AAO-HNS hosts simulation events to practice surgical skills during the Annual Meeting. OTO Media Gallery with surgical and radiological pictures to explore the anatomy of the head and neck.
American Rhinologic Society	Yes	Endoscopic Surgical Dissection Video Series; Patient Education Handouts; Webinar series; Evidence-based reviews; Interactive Case Learning series
American Head and Neck Society	Yes	Six AHNS Subspecialty Membership Sections w/available learning material; Surgical Videos; TORS Webinar Series
The American Osteopathic Colleges of Ophthalmology and Otolaryngology-Head and Neck Surgery (AOCOO-HNS)	Yes	ENT In a Nutshell podcast; Affiliate Program for Student Organizations; List and Contact Information for ACGME Residency Programs
Association for Research in Otolaryngology (ARO)	Yes	JARO Journal; Books of Interest list; ARO Seminar Series; ARO Educational Coffee Hours; ARO International Lecture Series; Vestibular Cafe Podcast; Journal Club
The Voice Foundation	Yes	Journal of Noice; Newsletters; Articles; Education Media database of lectures and webinars; Perceptual Voice Qualities Database as a research tool
National Otolaryngology Interest Group	Yes	Residency Match Guides; Pre-clinical and clinical medical education curriculum; upcoming educational webinars and workshops;
American College of Surgeons (ACS) - Otolaryngology / Head and Neck Surgery	Yes	Journal of ACS; discount on educational products at the annual conference
Dysphagia Research Society	Yes	DRSIE Monthly Webinar Series
American Cleft Palate-Craniofacial Association	Yes	CPC Journal; webinars; physician discussion boards; special interest groups; access to membership directory
Society for Ear, Nose, and Throat Advancement in Children (SENTAC)	Yes	Webinars; SENTAC podcast; patient education forms; research on common diagnoses

Note: Annual membership fees may not include free organizational journal access; costs for journal access vary.

Table 5. Educational Material Available to Medical Students.

and opportunities available to those aspiring to enter it. Regardless of background, all medical students should have equal access to the tools necessary for success.

to bridge these gaps, aiming to establish more inclusive and robust support systems for aspiring otolaryngologists.

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CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this analysis underscores the vital support that professional organizations offer to medical students pursuing otolaryngology, highlighting the significance of mentorship, research opportunities, and educational materials. It urges medical students to actively engage with organizations to enhance their career prospects in this field. In addition, limitations in mentorship, travel financial aid, and leadership roles point towards areas needing enhancement. These findings signal the necessity for future efforts

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